

"The Professionalization of Crime in Venezuela: How State Power Forged the Foundations of Transnational Organized Crime"

Introduction

In the early 2000s, the idea of crime becoming professionalized appeared paradoxical and could have sounded controversial. Even today, the existence of any institution, facility, group, or platform dedicating its efforts and services to training, improving, and perfecting criminal activities and their underlying logic may seem laughable.

In Venezuela, such a structure existed, where, in order to achieve certain objectives, the end justified the means.

After two decades of events and processes involving Venezuela's security and defense apparatus, we can now examine how the foundations of what we know today as Transnational Organized Crime originated.

The aim of this essay is to provide the reader with an analytical tool, supported by empirical knowledge, that reflects the author's perspective on how State Power, to the detriment of its fundamental role of protecting citizens, forged the foundations of Venezuelan Transnational Organized Crime.

Historical Context of the Professionalization of Crime in America, Guerrilla and Criminal Groups in Latin America

In America, there are precedents of certain structures whose subversive nature as non-state armed organizations required their members to possess a certain level of training.

Organizations such as the United Self-Defense Forces of Colombia, the Revolutionary Armed Forces of Colombia, and the National Liberation Army in the case of paramilitary and guerrilla groups, and criminal organizations such as the Medellín Cartel in Colombia and Los Zetas in Mexico.

These groups and organizations, primarily composed of individuals with prior military or police training, took on the task of providing knowledge and support to new members, aiming to strengthen their capabilities and achieve medium or high-level efficiency.

Criminal Training Strategies

Although it was neither exclusive nor excluding, their recruitment did not necessarily require members to have previous professional knowledge. However, the leadership was concerned with ensuring that members acquired general and diverse knowledge on how to handle weapons, operational and strategic management, and preventive actions for potential confrontations with rival groups or organizations over the control or dominance of an activity or territory, or against state security and defense agencies.

While the motivations of these groups might vary—whether ideological in some cases or economic in others—training was essential as a means to enhance effectiveness in their activities.

The Emergence of the Bolivarian Circles in Venezuela

In Venezuela, at the beginning of the 2000s, a social movement of citizen participation emerged, whose essence had a holistic scope within the framework of vulnerable societies. Its purpose was to address the needs of communities and foster greater social inclusion for marginalized or less privileged sectors.

Objectives of the Bolivarian Movement

In Venezuela, the then-president Hugo Chávez and his Bolivarian movement promoted the creation of the Bolivarian Circles, a structure aimed not only at including citizens under the premise of being "...a human, supportive, ethical, and avant-garde movement for the sustainable and sustained development of the country" (Book: *Fundamentos de Organización Círculos Bolivarianos*, undated), but also pursuing social justice.

Role of the Bolivarian Circles in Citizen Security

Among the activities described by this social movement, its organizational manual included a section dedicated to managing security within community sectors. In this section, titled "Integral Security and Prevention as Citizen Security," supported by Article 326 of the National Constitution of Venezuela, which states that national security is a shared responsibility of both the state and civil society, this constitutional article was employed to shape their objectives. They interpreted the concept of the nation from a territorial perspective, defining the role and commitment citizens should assume in situations involving conventional threats or aggression from other states. Citizens were expected to actively engage not only in safeguarding and protecting borders but also in managing internal security at the local level.

In a conventional state, the legitimate use of force is reserved for state security agencies, specifically intermediate and police forces¹. Nevertheless, the state allowed an overlap or usurpation of these functions by private individuals or non-state armed groups.

Training of the Bolivarian Groups

The executive branch and its government project undertook this initiative with three objectives, which created the necessity to train the members of these groups performing such tasks:

¹ In Venezuela, the intermediate forces refer specifically to the National Guard, whose legal framework allows them to operate in internal security management in collaboration with police forces, as well as to provide support for the country's external security and defense.

1. To responsibly train its members to develop a desired citizen security within communities by their own citizens.
2. To create ideologically aligned shock groups that could serve as an alternative force in case of a possible uprising or rebellion by state security and defense agencies.
3. To establish a non-state armed branch, allowing the use of force while exempting the state from the responsibility typically incurred by official security forces when using violence to suppress any demonstration, protest, or movement opposing their ideology or government project.

At this chronological stage of contemporary Venezuelan history, it becomes clearer to understand that the first objective served as justification for the not-so-hidden achievement of the other two.

Training at the Helicoide and the DISIP, Methods of Instruction

For this task, Hugo Chávez's government utilized agencies such as the former Directorate of Intelligence and Prevention Services (DISIP) to train members of the Bolivarian Circles.

Among the training provided were the use of firearms in their various forms, combat techniques and tactics, intelligence, counterintelligence, and others yet to be determined.

One of the locations used for this purpose was the now widely known Helicoide. Within its classrooms, an unknown number of members from the Bolivarian Circles received the necessary knowledge to achieve their objectives.

The groups typically consisted of around 30 or more individuals, all belonging to the same circle from a specific parish. Notably, all members knew each other, and there was constant vigilance and mistrust to detect potential outsiders. This demonstrated their clear awareness of their objectives and their fear of infiltration.

Control and Supervision of Training

Inside these classrooms, the trainers were skilled and active personnel from DISIP. The training content was specialized and similar to what could be provided at the institution's academy, except that it was delivered through intensive modules aimed at providing basic knowledge, for example, to carry out intelligence and counterintelligence activities.

As an initial premise, trainers warned trainees that if any staff from the facility asked them what they were doing inside, they should refuse to answer. This was paradoxical, given that within an intelligence agency like DISIP, responsible for obtaining privileged information, such a public secret could be maintained. It seemed to be something widely known within the institution, yet people pretended ignorance since instructions came directly from the highest levels of state power. The use of cell phones was prohibited, and these were collected and stored in a box by the instructor upon entering the classroom.

The training sessions lasted approximately two to three weeks, depending on the content, totaling around 90 to 135 hours of instruction. Lunch was provided to trainees in the Helicoide dining hall.

After attendance was taken and identities and names were confirmed, trainees' identity cards were collected. The second directive from trainers involved the following question: "Who voted against the government?" Using a list that contained the names of individuals who had voted against the government, these names were called out loud, and those identified were informed that they could not continue and had to leave the premises².

Credentials and Legitimization of the Bolivarian Circles

After completing the training, each participant was issued credentials affiliated with the Metropolitan Mayor's Office of Caracas. These credentials displayed a social intelligence logo and included a hierarchy, where the lowest rank was Sub-Inspector. On the reverse side, there was an inscription requesting cooperation from other security agencies in dealing with the credential holder. Additionally, it contained the phone number of one of the leaders of the Bolivarian Circles, Alberto Carías Pedraza, known as "El Chino Carías."³⁴ According to Salas (2017), Carías, who at one point served as the head of citizen security for the Metropolitan Mayor's Office of Caracas, was a Venezuelan revolutionary leader affiliated with the Tupac Amaru Revolutionary Movement (MRTA) in Venezuela and connected to various Bolivarian armed groups. His history, marked by armed struggle, clandestine activities, and political activism, made him a central figure in insurgent movements both within and outside Venezuela. He was both a fighter and strategist, participating in conflicts across Latin America, with close ties to figures such as Ilich Ramírez Sánchez, also known as "Carlos the Jackal."

From his involvement in urban guerrilla warfare to his role as deputy secretary of Citizen Security in Caracas, his life oscillated between radical militancy and political institutionalism. Accused of numerous violent acts and executor of what he called "popular justice," Carías moved within a world filled with conspiracies, betrayals, and extreme loyalties. His story was one of light and shadow, of struggle and persecution, alliances, and enmities.

² Although this material is the subject of study for another discipline, it arises as a reflection to understand that the vote in the December 2006 election was not secret, and that state agencies had full knowledge of the voting intention of each Venezuelan citizen.

³ It is recommended to watch the documentary by **THE UNDERGROUND DOCUMENTARY GROUP (2019), Tupamaro: Urban Guerrillas**, to better understand both the individual and the context. https://m.imdb.com/title/tt4128582/?ref=vp_vj_tt

⁴ It is recommended for a better understanding to read the blog by the author of "El Palestino", Antonio Salas, where he states: "Under his guidance, I would visit the DISIP building twice, receive paramilitary training, participate in the recording of 'terrorist' statements, and witness historical events firsthand." <https://loshombresquesusurranalasmaquinas.blogspot.com/2017/05/que-sentir-cuando-muere-alguien-que.html>

He passed away on May 28, 2017, in a Caracas hospital due to health complications, leaving behind a controversial legacy and a significant mark in the history of armed movements in Venezuela.

Credential issued to intelligence groups of the Bolivarian Circles.
Source: Confidential.

This credential is unpublished evidence not presented in other articles related to this subject; therefore, its significance is crucial for understanding the dynamics and scale of the situation at that time, and to document that the events described in this text indeed occurred. The holders of these credentials were not affiliated with or members of any official security institution. Nevertheless, security officials refrained from enforcing the law against these individuals to avoid sanctions from their superiors or higher authorities.

This leads us to consider the following:

- Why was it necessary to issue a credential with these characteristics to members of these groups if they were civilian in nature?
- If these individuals did not belong to official security forces such as the Caracas Police or the Metropolitan Police, why did they possess such credentials?
- Under what circumstances or conditions were they supposed to display them?
- Were these non-state armed groups overlapping or usurping the functions of official state security agencies?

All of the above lacks any legal or formal support or justification and is clearly an irregular act. Nevertheless, it was carried out. What is indeed clear is that the security agencies, Hugo Chávez, and his government were fully aware of what was happening, indicating that it was premeditated to achieve their own governmental objectives.

There were numerous violent incidents involving the so-called Bolivarian Circles, but they are particularly noted for their actions during the 2002 coup d'état and their vehement defense of the interests of their so-called Bolivarian Revolution.

There is evidence of DISIP officials publicly denouncing these events, expressing disagreement, and requesting action from Venezuelan justice authorities. Among these is the journalistic note published by Analítica on May 15, 2002, where a group of officials publicly denounced what had been occurring. However, the justice system made no significant progress due to pressure from the government⁵.

Both in the 2000s and currently, we have no doubt about the profile of an average member of the Bolivarian Circles. Although Carlos Rangel suggests that "not all Chavistas were cut from the same cloth," referring to the fact that initially there were people who saw hope in this project but withdrew when they saw deviations from its rhetoric, the majority of members consisted of individuals with criminal backgrounds and records for illegal activities, as well as others prone to crime.

These same individuals, already active within Venezuelan society and their communities, who dedicated their efforts to committing criminal acts, were given a golden opportunity to receive professional and specialized training, significantly enhancing their criminal capabilities.

Even though their commitment to Hugo Chávez's project was strong and many members moved on to occupy positions of responsibility in public administration, they never abandoned their previous practices. Instead, they joined or became members of criminal groups or organizations or served as links between criminal groups and the corrupt

⁵ "Former DISIP officials reported being expelled for refusing to train the Bolivarian Circles." <https://www.analitica.com/actualidad/actualidad-nacional/ex-funcionarios-de-la-disip-denunciaron-haber-sido-expulsados-por-negarse-a-entrenar-a-los-circulos-bolivarianos/>

state structure to obtain benefits and evade responsibility. Later, they expanded, changed their name to "colectivos," and spread across the entire national territory.

Conclusion

The exact number of people who participated in these training sessions remains unknown, but it was to be expected that sooner or later they would use this knowledge to consolidate stronger and more far-reaching criminal structures. Today, there is no doubt that many of them are leaders or members of Venezuelan-origin transnational organized crime organizations such as the "Tren de Aragua," or other affiliates throughout America and the world, where they have likely contributed by transferring their acquired knowledge to new members of these organizations, empirically and technically passing down the training they received through the state's human and professional resources.

The "Tren de Aragua" was not a coincidence; the State formed them, the State trained them, and the State maintains them, actively participating and being complicit in their existence. Today, there is no doubt that this is indeed the case.

Deylis Liscano-Sarcos

Email: Deyliscano@gmail.com

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